

D5.4 Stakeholder and industry representative engagement – Implementation summary

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¹ PU = Public

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Summary

BEGONIA Project

Europe is embarking on a transformative endeavour to modernise digital information usage, with a focus on enhancing the efficiency, sustainability, and connectivity of our energy and transportation sectors. At the core of this initiative lies the development of advanced Operational Digital Platforms (ODPs) that transcend national boundaries, leveraging state-of-the-art technologies such as data sharing, cloud computing, and network connectivity.

The BEGONIA Project is an EU-funded Coordination and Support Action that aims to expedite this digital transformation in the energy and transport sectors, analysing the most promising solutions and providing information to the European Commission to set up and fund future works project(s).

BEGONIA has the goal of identifying, studying and preparing the development of Operational Digital Platforms (ODPs) across different EU countries, starting from the identification of 10 cross-border and possibly cross-sector (energy and transport) use cases, meticulously shortlisting three based on predefined criteria, and evaluating their impacts through proof-of-concept implementation of their ODPs.

Summary of the Deliverable

This deliverable details the implementation of the stakeholder engagement strategy outlined under Task 5. 5.2 (T 5. 2) within Work Package five of the BEGONIA project. Its main aim is to record the processes, activities, and results of engaging stakeholders across the energy and transport sectors to support the development, refinement, and validation of Operational Digital Platform (ODP) use cases.

The BEGONIA project has aimed to identify, evaluate, and prepare a portfolio of cross-border and cross-sector use cases for ODPs across Europe. Stakeholder engagement has been a core element of this effort, ensuring that project outputs reflect actual market needs, regulatory priorities, and the viewpoints of industry, authorities, and research entities.

Key achievements of this deliverable include:

- Supporting WP 2 by swiftly mobilising networks to gather 14 initial use cases, validated through surveys and bilateral discussions with distribution system operators, logistics providers, ministries, and sectoral associations.
- Supporting WP 3 by consolidating six shortlisted use cases and obtaining commitments from potential implementation partners, related initiatives, and

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advisory bodies. Stakeholders provided structured feedback on scalability, cybersecurity, environmental impact, and alignment with EU policy.

- Supporting WP 4 by laying the groundwork for piloting activities, including mapping stakeholders for the three final use cases and confirming their interest in testing and validation, despite the temporary postponement of the call for proposals.
- Broadening engagement and dissemination through sectoral events, targeted communication campaigns, and collaboration with related projects (e. g., ECLIPSE, INSIEME), strengthening BEGONIA' s role in shaping the European digital transformation agenda.
- Maintaining ongoing dialogue with the European Commission and HaDEA, ensuring alignment on strategic priorities, validation of use case selection, and preparation for future funding mechanisms.

Overall, the deliverable demonstrates that BEGONIA has established a diverse and dedicated stakeholder community comprising distribution operators, ministries, port authorities, logistics firms, industry consortia, and EU- funded initiatives. This community has not only contributed to the design of use cases but also expressed clear interest in their piloting and subsequent implementation.

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Table of Acronyms

Acronyms	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
ODPs	Operational Digital Platforms
T5.1	Task 5.1
WP(s)	Work Package(s)
HaDEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
MITMA	Spain's Ministry of Transport, Mobility and Urban Agenda

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1. Introduction

1.1. Begonia Project

The BEGONIA Project aims to expedite the European digital transformation by analysing promising solutions emerging on the market and by providing recommendations to the European Commission (EC). Specifically, the project focuses on identifying, studying, and preparing the development of Operational Digital Platforms (ODPs) in the energy and transport sectors across various EU countries, with the aim of facilitating the setup and funding of future projects.

1.2. Work Package 5

Work Package (WP) 5, “Stakeholders' engagement, Dissemination and Knowledge transfer,” runs throughout the 27 months of the project and interacts with all other WPs with multiple objectives.

Firstly, WP5 plans and executes the Communication and Dissemination of Begonia. Communication and Dissemination include defining the project’s visual identity to support internal and external dissemination activities, as well as implementing a series of actions to facilitate engagement of a community of experts, including a dedicated web platform.

Secondly, WP5 aims to create a community of stakeholders to gather valuable market inputs and feedback, find partners, and provide other WPs with relevant market information and expert insights where necessary. To this end, WP5 actively involves experts, industry representatives, and relevant stakeholders in a value-added community for the project.

Finally, WP5 will transfer the project’s conclusions to the European Commission for the development of new calls for projects, and in the final months of the project, to the entities awarded the new project(s), offering information and support in the initial phases.

1.3. Task 5.2 and deliverable D5.4 scope

This deliverable presents the results of activities carried out within a broader Task, namely Task 5.2 (T5.2) – “Stakeholders' engagement, dissemination, and communication with the European Commission”. T5.2 aims to implement the stakeholder engagement strategy defined in T5.1, enabling stakeholders' engagement and facilitating the dissemination of knowledge throughout the project’s lifetime. Specifically, the following sub-objectives of the task have been identified as relevant for the deliverable:

1. To gather best practices and feedback from the community, providing inputs to WP2, WP3,

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2. To involve the necessary partners, identified through the outcomes of WP2 and WP3,
3. To provide specific inputs to WP4 on defining the governance bodies for the emerging infrastructure,
4. To engage with other EU-funded projects.

The proposed outcomes of the task included:

1. Organisation of webinars, workshops, and events (a minimum of 3 webinars, workshops, or events that can be held at EU trade fairs, plus organisation of 1 final event).
2. Use of a dedicated platform, mailing list, and questionnaires (a minimum of 5 questionnaires will be shared, and at least seven newsletters will be sent, one every 3 months from the start of the task).
3. Organisation of bilateral meetings between project representatives and stakeholders (both physical and virtual): at least 20 bilateral meetings will be organised.
4. Participation of project representatives in EU events and trade fairs (at least 2 EU events or trade fairs).
5. Maintain an open channel with the European Commission regarding the project's developments, sharing relevant information, gathering inputs, and conveying the outcomes of the tasks undertaken during the project, while providing support for defining the next call for projects.

1.4. Stakeholder engagement strategy

At the outset, BEGONIA recognised the importance of engaging with a wide range of stakeholders beyond its strong consortium of partners from five EU member states (Denmark, Spain, Austria, Belgium, and Greece). The initial strategy was designed to complement the consortium's expertise, gather diverse ideas, and build synergies with ongoing European initiatives.

Figure 1: Groups of stakeholders BEGONIA will be engaging with.

Stakeholders were divided into three main groups as illustrated in Figure 1:

1. **Experts and Advisory Board members** – key experts, associations, and organisations serving as a continuous sounding board for BEGONIA, providing Use Cases, access to missing expertise, or identifying project gaps.
2. **Interested entities and project followers** – engaged organically through communication and dissemination activities.
3. **Implementation partners** – winning consortium(s) of the call for proposals to be launched based on BEGONIA results through an EC tender process, primarily involved through knowledge transfer obligations linked to the ODP specifications.

While this framework set the starting point, stakeholder engagement developed throughout the project. Importantly, stakeholders were not only consulted to provide Use Cases but also played a key role in supporting the selection process and providing structured feedback, ensuring that their contributions created tangible value and enhanced the project's outcomes.

Experts and advisory board members who are part of the initial group played a prominent role in defining the scope of the researched use cases and validating their feasibility, considering not only the technical aspect but also the commercial and governance perspectives. Some of these partners also remained involved to support the implementation of internal pilots for selected use cases. Other stakeholders were mainly kept informed about the project's progress through regular updates organised at events, online, or via our dissemination channels such as newsletters, LinkedIn posts, etc. More information about these can be found in section 5.

Of particular relevance has also been the engagement with the European Commission and HaDEA. More details on this activity are available in section 5.

1.5. Structure of the remaining deliverable

Section 2 outlines stakeholder engagement activities necessary for conducting the assessment and pre-selection of initial use cases in WP2.

Section 3 details stakeholder engagement actions that aid in defining detailed specifications for pre-selected use cases and in making the final choice of use cases in WP3.

Section 4 describes relevant stakeholder activities to support the internal pilot projects of use cases in WP4.

Section 5 summarises all communication efforts with the wider community and specific engagement with other related EU projects and the EC.

Final conclusions are presented in section 6 of the document.

2. Stakeholder engagement for WP2 activities

2.1. Overview of stakeholder engagement strategy and activities

In the early stages of BEGONIA, stakeholder engagement was crucial in enabling the project to quickly identify and incorporate an initial set of promising use cases. This phase was especially focused on achieving the objectives of WP2.

Due to the urgency of this activity and the need for immediate, practical input, the project adopted a pragmatic and targeted approach to engagement. Instead of conducting a broad public consultation, BEGONIA partners utilised their existing networks, which they had developed during the proposal phase and refined during the first months of the project. This included direct outreach to trusted contacts and key actors already recognised as relevant stakeholders or potential contributors to the initiative.

This swift engagement method allowed BEGONIA to gather early insights efficiently, ensuring alignment with the technical and strategic criteria necessary for WP2's comparative assessment work.

Simultaneously, a more comprehensive stakeholder engagement strategy was devised to guide future interactions throughout the project's lifecycle. This strategy outlined long-term goals, tools, and engagement methods to be employed in the execution of WP2 and subsequent WP3 and WP4. Further details on the stakeholder strategy and the reasoning behind the initial outreach decisions are available in Deliverable 5.3.

The next subsection presents these findings and the main takeaways that informed the development and refinement of the first use cases chosen under WP2.

2.2. Initial use case collection for D2.1

A primary goal of WP2 was to identify a diverse range of use cases that illustrate the need for operational digital platforms supporting cross-border, cross-sector services in the energy and mobility sectors. These use cases should not only be developed by experts within the project but also mirror a broader market demand from various European stakeholders in relevant sectors.

To achieve this, the project initially identified a list of relevant stakeholders for engagement, gathering input from respective experts. A snapshot of this list at the start of the project is shown in the figure below. This initial stakeholder engagement took place from March to April 2024.

This stakeholder list has been continually updated and improved as the project has advanced.

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KIND	NAME	PURPOSE OF APPROACH			AREA OF FOCUS/EXPERTISE E.g. Energy, Transport, Regulation, Grids, ...
		USE CASES PROVIDER	USE CASES REVIEWER	LONG TERM INVOLVEMENT	
EU Projects	Int'Net		X	X	Energy, Data Spaces
	OMEGA-X	X	X		Energy, Data Spaces
	ENERSHARE				Energy, Data Spaces
	Data Cellar				Energy, Data Spaces
	EDDIE	X	X	X	Energy, Data Spaces
	Synergies				Energy, Data Spaces
	CETP				Energy, Data Spaces
	Green, Dat, AI				IoT/Edge AI
	Waterverse				IoT/Edge AI
	Open Continuum				IoT/Edge AI
	Mobi Spaces				IoT/Edge AI
	TRUSTEE				IoT/Edge AI
	TANGO				IoT/Edge AI
	TEADAL				IoT/Edge AI
	GLACIATION				IoT/Edge AI
	Twin EU				Grids and digital twins
	Interconnect				Smart Homes and Buildings
Unlock-CEI				IoT/Edge AI	
ODECN				IoT/Edge AI	
HEDGE-IoT				IoT/Edge AI	
ELEXIA		X	X	Energy, Data Spaces	
EU Initiatives	EIT, InnoEnergy				Energy, Regulation, Grids
	ETIP, SNET	X	X		Energy, Regulation, Grids
	W/G		X		Energy, Regulation, Grids
	Clean Energy transition partnership				Energy, Grids
	European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC)				Energy, Transport, Regulation
	DS4SSCC	X	X	X	Energy, Data
Associations	smarEn		X	X	Energy, Grids, Transport, Regulation
	AIO TI	?	X	X	
	OpenADR Alliance				
	Gala-X Data space business alliance				All sectors
	AVEFE				
	CHAdEMO				
	Mobility Portal Europe				
	APPLIA	?			Energy, Regulation
	Green Power Denmark		X		Grids
	UIC	X	X		Rail association
	FEHRL	X	X		Road Association
ALICE	X	X		Logistics association	
IWT	X	X		Inland Waterway Association	
ECTP	X	X	X	EU Construction Technology Platform	

KIND	NAME	PURPOSE OF APPROACH			AREA OF FOCUS/EXPERTISE E.g. Energy, Transport, Regulation, Grids, ...
		USE CASES PROVIDER	USE CASES REVIEWER	LONG TERM INVOLVEMENT	
Institutional and Regulatory bodies or experts	ACER		X		Grids, Energy, Regulation
	Florence School of	?	X		Regulation, Energy, Transport, Grids
	E, DSO		X	X	Grids, Energy, Regulation
	ENTSO-E		X		Grids, Energy, Regulation
	Danish Energy Agency		X	X	Data Spaces
	Agency for Digital Government		X	X	Data Spaces
	SDFI		X	X	Data Spaces
	Directorate-General for Roads (Transport Ministry of Spain)	X	X	X	Road management, maintenance and planning
	Cabildo de Tenerife (Canary Islands)	X		X	Traffic Management
	Cabildo de La Gomera (Canary Islands)			X	Traffic Management
	Valencia Port (Spain)			X	Port and logistic management
	Costanza Port (Romania)			X	Port and logistic management (inland waterways)
	Klaipeda Port (Lithuania)				Port and logistic management
	Infraestruturas de Portugal			X	Road and Railways management, maintenance and planning
	Brujas-Amberes Port				Port and logistic management (inland waterways)
	Puerto de Sevilla (Spain)		X	X	Port and logistic management (inland waterways)
Puerto de Vigo (Spain)		X	X	Port and logistic management	
National Research Centres	Energy systems Catalunya	X	X		
	CEA (FR)				
	Vito (BE)	X	X		
	Fraunhofer Energy Alliance (DE)				
	Alexandra Institute		X		Data Spaces
	CARTIF			X	Smart grids and buildings
	ITG				Smart grids and automation
	CIRCE				Generic
	CIMNE				Data Spaces
	TECNALIA				Generic
TEKNIKER				Automation and robotics	
University of Málaga			X	Data Spaces	
Companies	KONSTANT		X		Grids
	True Energy				EVs
	Spiri				EVs
	Nuvve				EVs
	EWI/Monta	X	X	X	EVs
	EVN	X	X	X	Grids, EVs
	Grupo Cuerva		X	X	
	Estabanell		X	X	
	Acciona		X	X	
	AISCAT Servizi		X		
EDP Portugal					
Sfera one					
Diggia					
DSQ/TSO	TREFOR	X	X	X	Grids
	Energinet	X	X	X	Data Spaces
		X	X	X	Grids, EVs

Figure 2: Preliminary list of identified stakeholders

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While the consortium partners reached out to all relevant stakeholders, there was a mixed response in the interest level of stakeholders. Some were keen to provide use cases, while others volunteered as use case reviewers or indicated further interest in supporting the project as it progresses. The figure above reflects the interest levels that the stakeholders have shown during their initial engagement.

For the stakeholders who provided use cases, the relevant stakeholder interactions and contributions are highlighted in the table below.

UC-ID	Title	Stakeholder
BEG.01	Operational digital platforms (ODP) for distribution grids	TREFOR (DSO), KONSTAN (DSO), AI-ENERGY
Nature of engagement		
The idea of this use case originated from the meetings with DSOs and stakeholders in Denmark involved in the SMARTDSO project. The results of those meetings were analysed and enriched by the inputs from academia and literature and resulted in the use case BEG.01.		

UC-ID	Title	Stakeholder
BEG.02	Digitalisation of energy storage and reuse in Data Centers	Provided by DTU (based on stakeholder input)
Nature of engagement		
The ideas and contents of the use cases come from meetings and discussions at conferences with stakeholders during Spring-Summer 2024 (Net Zero Data Centres, Energinet, Data Centres), Danish grant applications and research paper and has been improved using the feedback from the same and additional stakeholders. Most of the initially proposed services were rewritten due to the feedback from both stakeholders and the EC.		

UC-ID	Title	Stakeholder
BEG.03	Cross-border charging coordination and traffic management of electric trucks (ETs)	Postnord
Nature of engagement		
PostNord is a Nordic postal and logistics company. They have already started using electric trucks. The idea of the use cases was received from them and improved by desk research with special attention to the trends in electric mobility, EU targets on electric trucks' integration, and services related to them.		

UC-ID	Title	Stakeholder
BEG.04	Cross Border Electric Charging Project	CROSS-E, BME University Department of Networked Systems and Services at the Budapest University of Technology and Economics
Nature of engagement		
Blueprint engaged with Petrol (Slovenia), cross-border multiutility that is one of the partners in CROSS-E - CEF funded project rollout of charging infrastructure for electric vehicles along		

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key TEN-T corridors until 2026 as well as team from BME University responsible for development of AI supported traffic monitoring systems. The idea of the use case – particularly questions about cross-border aspects were received from them, with special attention to the trends in electric mobility, issues of planning charging stations, issues of dynamic pricing and commuter patterns and congestion across motorways as well as lack of traffic and charging forecasting with impact on the grids.

UC-ID	Title	Stakeholder
BEG.05	An ODP for interaction among EV owners, CPOs & grid	OMEGA-X Project
BEG.08	Cross-border virtual communities of RESs and and CLs	
Nature of engagement		
OASC engaged with the OMEGA-X project to source relevant use case ideas for BEGONIA. OMEGA-X provided two suitable use case as input to the project, which were further analysed. The outcomes of the analysis have inspired the definition of Use cases BEG.05 and BEG.08 in BEGONIA.		

UC-ID	Title	Stakeholder
BEG.06	A cross-border recommender tool and flexibility procurement mechanism for grid service	VITO
Nature of engagement		
OASC engaged with VITO to identify suitable cross-border energy applications. VITO contributed an example developed in the Interconnect project, which was further analysed in the consortium. The outcomes of the analysis have inspired the definition of Use cases UCI in BEGONIA.		

UC-ID	Title	Stakeholder
BEG.07	A unified way for changing the energy service provider in EU member states	Provided by BLP (based on a paper)
Nature of engagement		
The basic idea of the use case was from a paper published by a team that was working on the energy data space projects. The idea was analysed, improved, and finalized as the use case BEG.07		

UC-ID	Title	Stakeholder
BEG.09	Mobility 3.0	Ministry of Transport of Spanish Government
Nature of engagement		
The idea for this use case originated from meetings with the Spanish Ministry of Transport, where the BEGONIA project was presented in the context of identifying transport-related use cases (with CEMOSA leading this effort within the consortium). The Ministry shared their ongoing interest in developing advanced digital mobility solutions in the coming years, which directly inspired the definition of UC Mobility 3.0. Their vision of integrating vehicles, drivers, and road managers through real-time traffic updates and safety services aligned closely with BEGONIA's objectives. The Ministry's strategic priorities therefore served as the foundation for shaping the use case, ensuring its relevance and future applicability at national level.		

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UC-ID	Title	Stakeholder
BEG.10	Floating Car Data for dynamic insurance services	Provided by CEMOSA (based on stakeholder input)
Nature of engagement		
<p>This use case was proposed by CEMOSA, building on insights gained during the meeting with the Spanish Ministry of Transport. While the Ministry's focus was on mobility-related digital services, CEMOSA identified that the same V2X technology underpinning Mobility 3.0 could also generate value for the insurance sector. By extending the concept to insurers, the idea evolved into a platform that uses floating car data to develop personalised and dynamic insurance policies. This adaptation illustrates how stakeholder discussions with the Ministry inspired broader applications of the technology, opening opportunities for collaboration with insurance companies and vehicle manufacturers across Europe.</p>		

UC-ID	Title	Stakeholder
BEG.11	Digital permits for drone-based inspections in linear infrastructures	Provided by CEMOSA (based on stakeholder input)
Nature of engagement		
<p>The idea for this use case originated from discussions with Infraestruturas de Portugal together with the Spanish Ministry of Transport, in the context of cross-border coordination of transport infrastructures. During these exchanges, issues around responsibility for maintenance and the administrative processes for inspection were raised. This dialogue inspired the concept of a digital platform to streamline and secure the application process for drone-based inspections of linear infrastructures, particularly under cross-border conditions. The engagement with these two national authorities ensured that the use case responds to real regulatory and operational needs in managing shared infrastructure assets.</p>		

UC-ID	Title	Stakeholder
BEG.12	Smart Ports Operations	Autoridad Portuaria de Sevilla
Nature of engagement		
<p>This use case was developed following a meeting with the Port Authority of Seville (Autoridad Portuaria de Sevilla). At the time, they were already working on a project aimed at improving port logistics through the integration of multiple stakeholders. Building on these discussions, the idea for the Smart Port Operations UC emerged, leveraging AI cameras and drone systems integrated into the FIWARE platform (supported by CEF). The engagement with the Port Authority ensured that the UC addressed concrete operational challenges, while aligning with ongoing digitalisation efforts in the maritime sector. This interaction directly shaped the concept into a solution designed to improve safety, efficiency, and sustainability of port activities.</p>		

UC-ID	Title	Stakeholder
BEG.13	Carbon footprint of ports supply chain	Autoridad Portuaria de Vigo
Nature of engagement		

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The idea for this use case emerged from a meeting with the Port Authority of Vigo (Autoridad Portuaria de Vigo), who were actively engaged in the development of a tool to calculate the carbon footprint of transported goods within a wider consortium. Discussions highlighted the need for logistics operators to access reliable, transparent information to minimise environmental impact and provide consumers with accurate data on the footprint of their products. Building on this foundation, BEGONIA identified the opportunity to create a blockchain-based platform to track and update carbon emissions across the supply chain, from manufacturer to customer, through multiple ports. The engagement also included the Port of Leixões, involved in the same consortium, thereby reinforcing the cross-border dimension and strengthening the use case's practical relevance.

UC-ID	Title	Stakeholder
BEG.14	Inland Waterways Multimodality 4.0	Provided by CEMOSA (based on stakeholder input)
Nature of engagement		
This use case was introduced by CEMOSA , building on experience from a proposal coordinated by the company involving several inland waterways and multiple transport stakeholders. The discussions within that initiative underlined the importance of better coordination among transport operators, infrastructure managers, port authorities, and logistics hubs. Drawing on these insights, CEMOSA shaped the Inland Waterways Multimodality 4.0 UC as a platform to connect inland waterways with other modes of transport, providing real-time logistics and goods traffic updates. This engagement ensured the use case addresses concrete needs in multimodal transport efficiency and supports the transition towards greener modes such as railways and inland waterways.		

2.3. Use case selection for D2.2

After reviewing all received use case contributions from diverse stakeholders, the consortium drafted a total of 14 use cases for cross-sector and cross-border ODP-enabled services. These use cases reflected a mix of internal ideas and ideas captured from the initial market engagement.

The consortium then embarked on a second stakeholder engagement cycle to close the loop and gather further market feedback on the use case synthesis that had been performed. The purpose was to validate use case assumptions regarding technology, market interest, and potential benefits, and to identify barriers that the consortium might have overlooked.

Stakeholders were identified and selected based on their areas of expertise, encompassing Grids and DERs, E-Mobility, Data, and Transport & Logistics. Based on their specific knowledge and capabilities, each stakeholder was invited to review and provide feedback on up to three Use Cases, to maximise response rates and ensure focused contributions.

The goal was to receive confirmations from at least four stakeholders to act as reviewers for each of the Use Cases.

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Overall, between four and nine stakeholders per Use Case confirmed their availability. These stakeholders were provided with the use case description and evaluation form to provide us with feedback on the respective Use Case, which was collected through a survey circulated during the summer of 2024.

Given the summer period, not everyone who initially committed to the review was able to analyse the documents by the deadline. The table below summarises the allocations of stakeholders who participated in the survey and what use cases they reviewed.

Table 1: Mapping of reviewer allocations to identified use cases.

Reviewer	UC 1	UC 2	UC 3	UC 4	UC 5	UC 6	UC 7	UC 8	UC 9	UC 10	UC 11	UC 12	UC 13	UC 14
Energinet System Operator A/S	x	x	x			x								
Ministry of Transport and Sustainable Mobility (SPAIN)									x				x	
Enhancing Safety, Efficiency, and User Experience											x	x		
Alexandra Institute	x	x			x			x						
ACCIONA										x				x
smartEn		x		x		x								
Grupoo Diggia			x		x									
MaaS Alliance / EDIC			x	x					x					
FIWARE	x						x							
ANELL (DSO)	x													
Fundacion ValenciaPort													x	
Fraunhofer FIT					x				x	x				
CARTIF		x	x	x		x			x	x	x		x	
Digital for grids (EDDIE)	x		x					x						
Danish Energy Agency						x	x	x						
Autoridad portuaria de Vigo											x	x		x
VITO	x		x					x						
Number of reviews	6	3	5	3	3	4	2	4	4	3	3	2	3	2

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The survey asked for an overall assessment of the use case, with specific questions including:

- Strengths and weaknesses
- Ease of scalability of the UC
- Benefits of cross-sector integration
- Maturity level
- Robustness of cybersecurity
- Contribution to environmental protection
- Alignment with EU policies
- Clarity of concepts
- Alignment with stakeholder needs
- Ease of use

These inputs, contained in D3.3, proved highly valuable for the subsequent selection and merging process, which led to the 6 Use Cases further analysed in WP3, complementing the comments received from the European Commission and the technical feasibility assessments carried out by the BEGONIA team.

3. Stakeholder engagement for WP3 activities

3.1. Overview of stakeholder engagement strategy and activities

Following the initial stakeholder mapping and engagement efforts under WP2, which informed the identification and consolidation of the initial set of UCs, the activities in WP3 shifted strategy to focus on the technical feasibility, maximise impact and provide technical support for the six shortlisted use cases. These represent the most promising candidates for further development and potential implementation within the BEGONIA framework.

To align with this objective, the stakeholder engagement approach evolved to ensure deeper and more targeted interaction with relevant use case actors. As illustrated in Figure 3, this updated strategy pursued two main goals:

1. To secure commitment from companies or consortia willing to implement each of the six use cases, and potentially support their piloting within BEGONIA;
2. To collect feedback from a broader network of stakeholders and sister initiatives on the overall viability and interest in each of the proposed use cases.

In addition, cooperation with sister projects has been strengthened, both to create larger clusters of stakeholders interested in the project and to maximise communication efforts and the sharing of best practices. This activity will continue until the project is completed.

Figure 3: Stakeholder engagement Phase 2 schematization

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These engagement results were designed to inform the final selection process of the top three selected use cases, as detailed in Deliverable 3.3.

Target 1: Securing implementation interest

The first objective was achieved through a systematic review of all stakeholders previously contacted, briefed, or onboarded during earlier project phases. For each use case, at least one relevant actor with implementation potential was identified and engaged. A dedicated evaluation matrix was developed to assess each stakeholder's:

- expressed willingness to implement the use case.
- qualitative assessment of technical and financial readiness.
- potential for supporting piloting activities during the BEGONIA test phase.

This assessment allowed the consortium to map not only the overall engagement level but also the maturity and alignment between use case requirements and stakeholder capabilities. A summary of this mapping is provided in Table 1, which details the engagement status for each use case and partner type.

Table 2: Key stakeholders for implementation

USE CASE #	USE CASE NAME	BEGONIA PROMOTER PARTNER	STAKEHOLDER(S) FOR IMPLEMENTATION KIND	STATUS ALSO FOR PILOTING [Available / Missing]	QUALITATIVE ASSESSMENT ON CAPACITY OF IMPLEMENTING THE UC [Positive/Medium/Negative]
UC I	ELECTRICITY CUSTOMER CENTRIC ODP	CDK, DTU, BLP	Platform provider/Operator	Available	Medium
			Solution provider	Available	Medium
			TSO + DSO	Missing	
			Retailers	Missing	
UC II	AI-DRIVEN ODP FOR INTEGRATION OF EVS, ETS, RES AND GRID	BLP	Utility + DSO	Available	Positive
			CPO	Available	Positive
			Energy Community	Available	Medium
UC III	DIGITALIZATION OF DATA CENTERS	DTU, CDK	Data Center Associations	Available	Positive
			TSOs	Missing	
			Data centers	Available	Positive
UC IV	DIGITAL PERMITS FOR DRONE-BASED INSPECTIONS IN LINEAR INFRASTRUCTURES	CEMOSA	National civil aviation authority	Missing	
UC V	SMART PORTS OPERATIONS	CEMOSA	Port Authority	Available	Negative
UC VI	CARBON FOOTPRINT OF PORTS SUPPLY CHAIN	CEMOSA	Port Authority	Available	Positive
			Port Authority	Available	Positive

Target 2: Widening external feedback

To address the second objective, a more comprehensive and structured outreach campaign was conducted in coordination with the project's communication team. This effort aimed to extend the BEGONIA ecosystem by engaging with external experts,

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organisations, and sister projects not previously involved in the earlier engagement rounds.

The process included:

- individual calls and presentations introducing BEGONIA's objectives and use cases.
- onboarding new stakeholders into the project's Microsoft Teams environment to facilitate long-term communication and updates.
- dissemination of a targeted survey to gather structured input on both the overall project direction and each of the six use cases.

This expanded outreach helped test the appeal and realism of the use cases beyond the initially involved technical and institutional circles, contributing to their iterative refinement and strengthening their real-world alignment.

Overall, stakeholders consulted during this phase expressed a high level of interest in the BEGONIA use cases. The feedback highlighted not only the relevance of the proposed solutions to current challenges in the energy and transport sectors but also a clear interest in contributing to or even leading their implementation.

Survey results confirmed:

- a perceived relevance of the use cases in addressing pressing sectoral issues (average score: 4.33/5),
- a general willingness to engage in implementation activities (average score: 4.33/5).

The highest level of interest clustered around four use cases: UC I, UC II, UC III, and UC V. These use cases were most frequently selected as preferred candidates for both implementation (Figure 4) and piloting (Figure 5).

Figure 4: Survey results - Which Use Case(s) do you consider interesting or relevant to participate in the future implementation?

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Figure 5: Survey results - Would you be willing to participate in some simple tests which imply some data sharing and which could help us in validating a UC?

To provide a holistic view of stakeholder input, both in dedicated meetings and survey results, a final summary table was produced (see Table 3), capturing the interest and availability status of each stakeholder consulted. For privacy reasons, company and contact names have been anonymised.

Table 3: Interested stakeholders - Implementation and piloting

STAKEHOLDER NAME (COMPANY OR INSTITUTION)	KIND	CONTACT PERSON	Poll sent	INTEREST IN UCs (Potentially)						INTEREST FOR PILOTING						
				UC I	UC II	UC III	UC IV	UC V	UC VI	UC I	UC II	UC III	UC IV	UC V	UC VI	
XXX	Solution provider	XXX	X	O								P				
XXX	Retailer	XXX	X													
XXX	Investigation center	XXX	X				O									
XXX	EPC	XXX	X	O	O	O										
XXX	Solution provider	XXX														
XXX	Investigation center	XXX	X													
XXX	Association/Initiative	XXX	X													
XXX	Data center association	XXX	X			X							P			
XXX	Solution provider	XXX	X	X	X	X						C				
XXX	Solution provider	XXX	X	X	X	X			X			C	C	C		
XXX	Solution provider	XXX	X													
XXX	DSO and Retailer	XXX	X													
XXX	Management	XXX	X	X	X			X				C	C			
XXX	Solution provider	XXX			X								P			
XXX	Research institute	XXX	X				O									
XXX	Solution provider	XXX	X	X	X					X			C	C	C	
XXX	Research institute	XXX														
XXX	Solution provider	XXX	X	O	O											O
XXX	EU project	XXX	X													
XXX	Solution provider	XXX	X	X	X				X			C				
XXX	Port authority	XXX	X							X						P
XXX	Solution provider	XXX	X	X	X	X						C	C	C		
XXX	Association/Initiative	XXX	X	X	X				X			C				
XXX	Solution provider	XXX	X						X	X					C	C
XXX	Expert	XXX	X			X							P			
XXX	Solution provider	XXX	X		X								P			
XXX	Utility	XXX	X		X											
XXX	Solution provider	XXX														
XXX	Solution provider	XXX	X				O									
XXX	EU project	XXX														
XXX	Sister project	XXX	X													
XXX	Solution provider	XXX	X													
XXX	Aggregator	XXX														
XXX	Investigation center	XXX	X	X	X							C	C			
XXX	Port authority	XXX	X	O	O			O	O	O		C	C		C	C
XXX	Port authority	XXX	X		X	X	X		X							
XXX	Port authority	XXX	X						O	X					C	P
XXX	Solution provider	XXX	X	X	X							P	C		C	

The matrix uses the following notation:

- X: Confirmed, concrete interest in implementing the use case.
- O: Open to future implementation.
- C: Confirmed willingness to support piloting activities.
- P: Open to exploring piloting involvement.

This coding allowed the consortium to distinguish between initial interest and actual commitment, supporting the comparative scoring and prioritisation process in Deliverable 3.3.

Strategic use of results

The findings from this second engagement phase were crucial in refining the scoring system used for selecting the final use cases. The stakeholder dimension was explicitly incorporated into the evaluation methodology in D3.3, ensuring that stakeholder commitment and strategic alignment influenced the prioritisation of the top three use cases. For more details on the use case selection and scoring methodology, see D3.3.

3.2. Use case-specific stakeholder engagement

This section offers further details on stakeholder engagement for each of the six initially selected use cases. For each use case, it describes the specific stakeholder engagement strategy, the nature of interactions that occurred, the main outcomes, and how they influenced the detailed use case specifications, as well as the commitments obtained from stakeholders.

3.2.1. Stakeholder engagement for UCI

Engagement strategy

UCI results from merging UCs 6, 7, and 8. These use cases originated from other projects, which we refined through desk research and then developed into three separate use cases. UC6 was proposed by OASC and VITO. OASC also proposed UC8 in collaboration with the OMEGA-X project, while UC8 was also suggested by Blueprint Energy. As a result, we did not have direct contact with specific stakeholders while defining and improving the use case. Nonetheless, the significance of the three use cases and their final merged version was confirmed in workshops and meetings. The strategy involved identifying stakeholders who could validate the concept of the virtual community and the provision of grid services for low- and mid-voltage grids, as well as advise on the real-life implementation of data space frameworks as part of UCI. Priority was given to organisations with successful implementations of energy community and customer-oriented platforms that rely on data spaces and smart energy management.

Meetings held

Stakeholder engagement sessions took place during workshops with the EC and a meeting with the Alexandra Institute in Denmark (June 2024), leading to the publication of this use case in their use case catalogues [1], thus validating the use case. The UC was also presented to the 4i4 company for discussion on potential collaboration for testing ODP solutions (February 2025). The use cases were showcased at several EU project meetings with interested partners, securing commitments from the University of Bari, the Danish Technological Institute, and other participants (May 19, 2025). Six use cases for energy data spaces are available online¹.

Main conclusions:

- Data space implementation should be partially completed as part of the ODP, contrary to previous conclusions by the partners.
- The flexibility procurement should be tested on actual flexible devices, e.g., HVAC systems.
- The digital twins of flexible systems, e.g., data centres, should be created based on actual operational profiles, which are difficult to obtain.

Commitments obtained:

- The University of Bari agreed to participate in funding applications to support the Begonia ODP piloting as part of the activities involved in establishing energy management systems at the Port of Bari.
- Participation of Graz Institute of Technology in piloting. They will provide data centre simulators and typical profiles to significantly contribute to the mid-voltage grid flexibility.
- DTI is committed to supporting customer flexibility procurement testing by providing HVAC endpoints for mobile app-based actuation.

3.2.2. Stakeholder engagement for UCII

Engagement strategy:

The approach involved identifying stakeholders who could benefit from the services proposed in UCII by integrating EV charging, distributed renewable generation (and storage) into energy communities and marketplaces. The initial candidates were actors already active in e-mobility, smart charging, and traffic data analysis, such as Petrol in Slovenia and BME University in Hungary, who had shaped the original UC4 concept. They

¹ <https://alexandra.dk/download-viden-om-data-spaces/>

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provided first-hand knowledge of mobility challenges, charging infrastructure, and AI-driven traffic anomaly detection.

In the next step, stakeholders with complementary expertise were engaged to enrich the use case. These included flexibility platform providers (Hungarian Smart Charging Kft solutions company), community-scale operators (Green Point in Austria), and peer-to-peer renewable marketplaces (OurPower in Austria). To ensure scalability and alignment with national system needs, large utilities and innovation teams (Wien Energie and Verbund) were invited to validate the feasibility of integrating UCII outcomes with wider grid and storage services.

Meetings held:

- **Petrol (Slovenia):** Two workshops in 2024 refined UC4 and later UCII, leading to its inclusion in Petrol's use case catalogues. Follow-up workshops took place in 2025. Discussions centred on e-mobility challenges, grid integration, and opportunities for cross-border charging services.
- **BME University (Hungary):** Several workshops in 2024 explored coupling BME's traffic anomaly detection platform with EV charging forecasts to demonstrate predictive flexibility.
- **Smart Charging Kft / EKT Solutions (Hungary):** Meetings in March 2025 examined how their flexibility platform, active in Hungarian markets, could integrate EV smart charging into balancing and reserve markets.
- **Green Point (Austria):** Meetings in Wiener Neustadt in 2024 validated their potential role in planning charging and storage integration, linking building-level PV, storage, and charging assets to flexibility experiments.
- **OurPower (Austria):** Exchanges throughout 2024–2025 considered how their renewable electricity marketplace could incorporate flexibility signals from EV charging and community storage.
- **Wien Energie (Austria):** An exploratory meeting in 2025 assessed how UCII results could be embedded in Wien Energie's smart city mobility and electrification strategies.
- **Verbund (Austria):** A meeting in 2025 with Verbund's storage innovation representative discussed how distributed storage and charging loads could support use cases and impact the grids.

Main conclusions:

- Grid impacts from large-scale charging remain a key challenge. Petrol emphasised the need to align cross-border charging infrastructure with flexibility services to avoid local congestion.

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- ET charging has emerged as more promising than EVs, due to higher, more predictable loads and stronger business cases for fleet operators to engage in flexibility markets.
- Effective demand response requires coordination between charging platforms and DSOs/TSOs; current frameworks for procurement and settlement are not yet mature enough across all three countries.
- Integration with renewable generation is essential. Curtailment can be reduced if ET charging is shifted to periods of high RES availability.
- Community and cooperative actors (e.g. OurPower, Green Point) can add value, but large-scale integration depends on grid operators and utilities adopting common interoperability standards.

Commitments obtained:

- **Petrol** provided preliminary commitment to support UCII development, and to provide infrastructure access for piloting grid-integrated charging services but without direct data sharing/access and they expressed that in line with the development of ODP call planned for end of 2025.
- **BME University** agreed to share sample data their traffic anomaly detection platform to help forecast electric vehicle charging demand and link results with flexibility services.
- **Smart Charging / EKT Solutions (Hungary)** did not commit to testing ET charging integration but sharing some sample data outputs on their flexibility platform to explore cross-border interoperability.
- **Wien Energie** expressed willingness to evaluate scaling opportunities within Vienna's mobility electrification initiatives.

In addition, several internal meetings with the BLP team were organized to ensure regulatory compliance with the use cases.

3.2.3. Stakeholder engagement for UCIII

Engagement strategy:

The approach was to identify stakeholders who can benefit from the services proposed in UCIII by leveraging load transfer across spatial and temporal dimensions or reducing costs through energy management. The initial candidates were data centres that had already indicated their preferences during past DTU Compute projects. They understand the challenges and opportunities within the Data Centre sector and aim to comply with emerging EU regulations on sustainability. In the next step, stakeholders with in-depth

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knowledge of rules and emerging technologies, such as data spaces, thermal energy management innovations, and grid integration, were invited to provide their feedback.

Meetings held:

Two data centre representatives from the Cool Data project, during April 2024 (Naviar and Energy Cool), developed ideas for the use case. Naviar was interested in supporting renewable integration and heat pumps, while Energy Cool had a broader focus on digital solutions for energy management and planning new data centre equipment. Several meetings in 2024 were held with Net Zero Data Centres (active contributors during Spring-Summer 2024 and 2025), one with Navitas DC (07-03-2025), one with Energinet (June 2024), and several meetings with Alexandra Institute (June 2024, April 2025) to validate the use case and help shape the Danish agenda to reflect the UCIII objectives. Net Zero Data Centres held meetings with 50Hz and Data4 and agreed to support a pilot.

Main conclusions:

- Heat storage and rejection to the district heating grid or for local reuse poses challenges due to design inefficiencies. Integration with demand response and between sectors is essential (e.g. AI workload transfer between GPUs would increase heat output).
- Challenges of setting up and procuring grid services using UPS batteries due to the lack of an advanced control framework that can be integrated into the data centres.
- Formulating the cross-border use case is necessary to integrate renewables across borders, coordinating different assets through the platform.
- Integration between data spaces and technical systems is a challenge that needs to be resolved at the data centre level (SCADA requires interfaces to the external world that ensure filtering and sovereign exchange of operational data).
- TSOs are currently lacking a method for monitoring data centre flexibility to utilise it as useful electrical grid inertia.

Commitments obtained:

- *Net Zero Data Centres* is committed to acting as a testbed for data centre energy system testing and providing access to infrastructure for piloting.
- *Navitas* agreed to act as a BRP and demonstrate heat rejection and the impact of cross-sector flexibility in the event of successful Danish funding.
- *Net Zero Data Centres* confirmed their willingness, as well as that of their partners, to proceed with the procurement of the ODP for energy storage management experiments, in collaboration with the data centre managed by *Energy Cool*, once the software is ready.
- All other partners agreed to provide technical support for the further development of the use cases.

3.2.4. Stakeholder engagement for UCIV

Engagement strategy:

The approach was to first engage with national authorities responsible for transport and infrastructure regulation to confirm the administrative importance of the UC, and then broaden the dialogue to include cross-border counterparts and private operators to gather both regulatory and operational insights. The engagement involved bilateral technical meetings and exploratory sessions aimed at identifying real bottlenecks in the current inspection permitting processes.

Meetings held:

A total of four structured meetings took place. Two meetings were held with MITMA (Spain's Ministry of Transport, Mobility and Urban Agenda), focusing on the complexity of current permitting frameworks and the potential role of digitalisation to expedite approval processes. One meeting was held with Infraestruturas de Portugal (IP), broadening the scope to include the cross-border dimension. One meeting was conducted with Acciona, providing the private sector perspective on the operational needs of inspection contractors.

Main conclusions:

- The current permitting process is slow, fragmented, and heavily reliant on paperwork, leading to delays in critical infrastructure maintenance.
- Cross-border inspections (e.g., the Guadiana International Bridge) increase complexity, as operators must adhere to two different national regulatory frameworks.
- Digitalisation through a cross-border ODP would improve safety and efficiency while reducing administrative burdens.

Commitments obtained:

- MITMA expressed willingness to provide regulatory input and technical validation to ensure alignment with Spanish procedures. *Infraestruturas de Portugal* is committed to collaborating in defining cross-border permit workflows and validating the solution in the context of the Guadiana Bridge. No commitment from *Acciona*.
- Piloting opportunities:
 - The most prominent pilot discussed was the *Guadiana International Bridge* between Spain and Portugal. Both MITMA and IP considered it a highly symbolic and practical testbed, since it is jointly managed and requires coordination between two national frameworks.

- Support offered:
 - Technical: *MITMA* and *IP* offered access to regulatory experts and technical staff to guide the adaptation of permitting processes.
 - Economic/operational: in-kind resources (staff time, technical input, access to infrastructures) for piloting and testing activities.

3.2.5. Stakeholder engagement for UCV

Engagement strategy:

The approach for UCV centred on engaging the Port Authority of Seville (APS) as the main stakeholder and organising discussions on ongoing and future digitalisation initiatives. The engagement strategy was designed to connect APS's local operational challenges with wider European policy and innovation frameworks, ensuring the UC addressed real needs while aligning with EU standards and climate neutrality goals.

Meetings held:

Two structured meetings were held with APS, supported by ongoing exchanges with CEMOSA. These sessions addressed both infrastructure topics (rail electrification, port energy management, inland/coastal operations) and digital innovation opportunities (integration with FIWARE, AI-driven monitoring, and synchro-modal logistics).

Main conclusions:

- *APS* faces significant logistical inefficiencies due to limited synchro-modality with rail and dependency on tidal schedules.
- The electrification of port rail access was discussed as a key priority.
- Energy consumption management is highly fragmented, with multiple public and private actors using different points of supply. Digitalisation is essential for monitoring and optimisation.
- *APS* is committed to aligning with EU initiatives such as TAFTSI (Telematic Applications for Freight, Directive 2016/797/EC), under the umbrella of Valencia Port and related projects (e.g., SAFARI – Horizon Europe).
- As Seville is among the 100 EU Mission Cities for Climate Neutrality, the UC should also support the integration of renewable energy and promote energy efficiency.

Commitments obtained:

- *APS* is committed to acting as a testbed for the proposed smart port solutions and to providing access to infrastructures for piloting.

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- They confirmed their willingness to integrate results into their digital transformation roadmap, particularly regarding AI-based monitoring and synchro-modal management.
- *APS* expressed readiness to involve other stakeholders (fleet managers, logistics operators, energy providers) to validate and co-develop the UC.
- Piloting opportunities:
 - The electrification and digital monitoring of the rail entry to the port were identified as a concrete pilot, with potential to test energy efficiency and synchronous modal integration.
 - Use cases for energy consumption digitalisation across multiple supply points in the port were also proposed, leveraging *FIWARE*-based tools and AI.
 - The expansion of the port by 2 km towards the city presents an additional opportunity for pilots to link port operations with urban energy and mobility systems.
- Support offered:
 - Technical: *APS* intended to provide operational data, access to port facilities, and involvement of their technical staff.
 - Economic/Operational: *APS* demonstrated a willingness to contribute in-kind resources, including dedicated staff time, infrastructure access, and coordination with existing EU-funded projects.

3.2.6. Stakeholder engagement for UCVI

Engagement strategy:

The engagement process for UCVI was built on an existing collaboration between the Port Authority of Vigo (APV), the Port of Leixões (APDL), and consortium partners already working on carbon footprint (CF) calculation tools. The strategy was to shift from fragmented departmental data practices to a shared, cross-border solution based on blockchain and API integration, ensuring transparency, traceability, and alignment with EU decarbonisation targets.

Meetings held:

A total of three structured meetings took place with APV, supplemented by bilateral exchanges with APDL and other consortium members. Discussions progressed from identifying data inefficiencies and siloed practices to proposing concrete technical solutions for interoperability. Interest was also expressed in logistics digitalisation

projects (Galicia–Portugal corridor, resource booking platforms) as well as a dedicated CF tool with advisory services to help companies reduce emissions.

Main conclusions:

- There is a clear need for interoperable systems that unify CF calculations across logistics and port operations.
- Tools should go beyond mere compliance, providing practical benefits for logistics operators, port authorities, and citizens.
- Governance involving multiple administrations (such as Vigo’s dry port and cross-border operations with Portugal) is complex and requires harmonised frameworks.
- Improvements in efficiency within container and vehicle terminal operations directly lead to cost savings and a reduction in carbon emissions.
- Stakeholders welcomed the selection of UCVI, affirming that it addresses an urgent operational and policy need. They appreciated the pragmatic approach: emphasising API integration instead of new sensor acquisition, to optimise resource use and deliver immediate additional value.

Commitments obtained:

- APV and APDL jointly proposed allocating the pilot’s full budget (around € 30,000) to develop an API for seamless integration of their existing tools, such as Vigo’s CF platform and Leixões’ Digital Cologistics.
- Both authorities committed to providing real-world emission data from road and maritime transport.
- They also agreed to prepare a joint technical sheet outlining existing infrastructures (sensors, systems, databases) to guide integration.
- Piloting opportunities:
 - The pilot will test a cross-border API connecting APV and APDL tools, enabling joint CF monitoring across Galicia and Portugal.
 - The system will calculate CF for transported goods, ensuring traceability, validation, and interoperability across both ports.
 - Existing infrastructures (sensors and platforms already deployed) will supply data to the pilot without additional costs.
- Support offered:
 - Technical: APV and APDL committed to providing access to existing platforms (e.g., Digital Cologistics), operational data, and staff time for integration and testing.
 - Economic/operational: Both ports agreed to dedicate in-kind resources (data, infrastructures, technical expertise) and validated that the API could be developed within the initial € 30.000 budget.

4. Stakeholder engagement to support WP4 activities

4.1. Overview of stakeholder engagement strategy and activities

The third and final phase of stakeholder engagement will continue until the end of the project. While the primary focus is on supporting WP4 activities, the scope extends further, encompassing the upcoming call for works and the subsequent follow-up project aimed at implementing one or more of the final BEGONIA Use Cases.

A draft plan for this phase was prepared at the conclusion of WP3, structured around two main objectives (see the Figure below):

Figure 6: Stakeholder Engagement Phase 3 draft plan

The primary aim was to secure and coordinate stakeholder involvement in testing each selected Use Case. The second aim was to maximise the visibility of the call for proposals,

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ensuring broad participation from capable consortia. The latter effort had already been initiated several months prior to this plan.

For the first aim, a comprehensive mapping of stakeholders and confirmation of their availability has been carried out (see the following Table):

Table 4: Mapping of stakeholders involved for piloting, Phase 3

USE CASE #	USE CASE NAME	PROMOTER PARTNER	FUNCTIONALITIES TO BE TESTED	STAKEHOLDER INVOLVED KIND	STAKEHOLDER INVOLVED NAME	INTERNAL BEGONIA CONTACT	STATUS [To contact / Contacted / Agreement / Ready for piloting]
UC I	ELECTRICITY CUSTOMER CENTRIC ODP	DTU		Platform provider/Operator	XXX	OLIVO	Contacted
				Platform provider/Operator	XXX	DTU	Contacted, agreed to contribute
				Platform provider/Operator	XXX	OLIVO	Contacted, agreed to contribute
				System operator	XXX	DTU	
				Retailer	XXX	DTU	
UC II	AI-DRIVEN ODP FOR INTEGRATION OF EVS, ETS, RES AND GRID	BLP		Utility (retailer and DSO)	XXX	BLP	Contacted, agreed to contribute
				Platform provider/Operator	XXX	BLP	Contacted, pending next steps
				Smart Charging (CP) operator	XXX	BLP	Contacted, pending next steps
				RES operator, technology partner	XXX	BLP	Contacted, agreed to contribute
UC III	DIGITALIZATION OF DATA CENTERS	DTU		Data Center Association	XXX	DTU	Contacted, agreed to contribute
				Data centers	XXX	DTU	Contacted, agreed to contribute
				TSO	XXX	DTU/NZH	

In preparation for the pilot, it was agreed to start with an internal testing phase before involving external stakeholders. Accordingly, consortium members scheduled a coordination meeting for early September to define testing timelines, budget allocations, and functionalities to be evaluated. Only after this phase would formal agreements with stakeholders be finalised.

In any case, the project partners have undertaken dedicated engagement activities for each of the three final use cases. Further details on these activities are provided in the following subchapters.

However, it is important to note that progress on the stakeholder engagement plan was paused at the beginning of July 2025 following the cancellation of the call for works. This event altered perspectives and made it necessary to restructure the engagement strategy. Some stakeholders had confirmed their participation in the pilot due to their interest in the call for works. Without it, alternative approaches will be needed to maintain their commitment. A revised plan is currently being drafted, outlining the new stakeholder engagement strategy to be implemented from October 2025 until the end of the project, considering the revised project goals, timeline, and the updated communication strategy under review. As a result, the table above will be updated accordingly during October and possibly November 2025.

4.2. Stakeholder engagement to support pilot for UCI

During the first half of 2025, meetings with UCI stakeholders expressed interest in UCIII piloting, including HVAC for buildings to provide devices for flexibility aggregation and

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grid services. At the Data Spaces community meeting in April 2025, Energinet showed interest in supporting the piloting of UCI and DTU within a single radial distribution network, and DTU followed up on this communication in subsequent correspondence.

During the EU research meeting on energy system digitalisation (19-05-2025), DTI expressed interest in contributing to UCI piloting by providing their HVAC endpoints for testing flexibility services, grid services, and user apps for controllable load management. At the same meeting, the University and Port of Bari, along with their electrical grid control project collaborators, expressed interest in the UCI piloting in exchange for access to grid management solutions from the project.

On 25-06-2025, a meeting with ITG (Spain) confirmed their commitment to contribute to the piloting after applying for common EU funding during autumn.

4.3. Stakeholder engagement to support Pilot for UCII

During the last quarter of 2024, workshops and meetings with UCII stakeholders confirmed strong interest in piloting. Initial contacts centred on Petrol, a DSO and utility company representing grid aspects. Petrol built on their experience from the CEF-funded CROSS-E project, where charging infrastructure was deployed for both EVs and ETs, providing regulatory and technical context for cross-border charging optimisation and grid services.

In November 2025, workshops in Wiener Neustadt were held with Green Point, which acts not only as an energy service provider supplying smart buildings and energy communities with charging infrastructure, but also as an installer of rooftop solar panels and storage systems. These meetings confirmed Green Point's interest in supporting UCII piloting through their community-scale infrastructure. Similar discussions took place with Wien Energie and its parent company Wiener Stadtwerke, operators of Vienna's city grid. They expressed interest in evaluating UCII once more information is available during the prototyping phase.

The concept of managing charging flexibility was further developed with BME – Department of Networked Systems. Smart Charging Kft explored integration of their flexibility platform with heavy fleet charging, while BME focused on applying their traffic anomaly forecasting to optimise charging point use and predict flexibility potential. BLP followed up these discussions through subsequent correspondence.

In early 2025, Petrol expressed interest in contributing directly to UCII piloting by providing one of their CPO endpoints for testing flexibility and grid services, particularly in simulations involving dynamic pricing. Stakeholder interest in developing an end-user app consolidating prices across the cross-border region remained limited, but ET fleet

operators demonstrated strong engagement, seeing value in UCII piloting in exchange for access to grid management, forecasting, and dynamic price-based market solutions.

4.4. Stakeholder engagement to support Pilot for UCIII

During the first half of 2025, several stakeholders contributed to defining the UCIII pilot case: the Alexandra Institute, Energinet, and other Data Spaces community members expressed interest in supporting the piloting of UCII in April 2025, and DTU agreed to notify potential partners when their involvement was required.

On 14-02-2025, a discussion on collaboration in UCIII piloting took place with representatives from Net Zero Data Centers, where the involvement of EU stakeholders in the follow-up and letters of support (from TSOs and DCs) were discussed as prerequisites for their participation, as well as the provision of infrastructure, test beds, and co-funding.

During the meeting held on 15-03-2025, they also contributed to detailing the UC common piloting plan and potential application for Danish funding to support piloting, which would involve providing infrastructure for data centre load testing and heat reuse.

The follow-up meeting on 05-07-2025 with their director at the Conference on the Future of Digital Investments in the EU on 3 July 2025 resulted in an agreement to seek funding support for the piloting and subsequent phases. This led to a meeting with international stakeholders on 05-08-2025 and the submission of a regional funding application jointly with other Danish stakeholders on 07-08-2025.

5. Communications and wider engagement

5.1. Communication activities with the wider public

All communication activities in BEGONIA have been closely aligned with the project's stakeholder engagement objectives. Given the technical and specialised nature of the work, efforts were not directed towards a broad general audience but instead targeted at experts, decision-makers, sister projects, and other relevant stakeholders. **Communication channels such as LinkedIn, X, the BEGONIA Knowledge Hub, and the project newsletter (*BEGONIA Digest*)** were used strategically to reach this audience, ensuring that information shared was both relevant and impactful.

A central element of this strategy has been BEGONIA's participation in sector-specific events and presentations. The project showcased its results and key takeaways at major conferences such as **ENLIT 2024 (Milan)**, **FEL2050 (2024 and 2025 editions, Málaga)**, the **Port Innovation Days 2024 in Oporto (October)**, and the **SmartEn Summit in Brussels (May 2025)**.

BEGONIA also engaged as an attendee in several high-visibility events, including the **1st CEF Digital Community Event (Brussels, October 2024)** of , **Med Power (Athens, November 2024)**, Innovation Projects in **Energy (Madrid, 2025)**, **Smarter E (Munich, May 2025)**, and **EUSEW (Brussels, June 2025)**. OASC was also invited to present BEGONIA as part of a keynote at the **Smart City Summit & Expo (Taipei, March 2025)**.

In addition, the project contributed to sectoral podcasts, such as the one organised by ENLIT. These activities not only increased visibility and dissemination of BEGONIA's perspectives and results but also allowed for strengthening dialogue and collaboration with other initiatives, leading, for example, to **the cooperation agreement with ECLIPSE** and the **connection established with the INSIEME project**, detailed in the next section.

Simultaneously, the dedicated **BEGONIA Teams platform** has played a key role in engaging stakeholders more directly. Crafted from the beginning as a collaborative space, it enables participants to access project documents, offer feedback, and stay informed about progress and updates. All stakeholders involved in surveys and piloting activities are part of this platform, which remains an active tool for cooperation and knowledge sharing. At the time of writing, **60 stakeholders are registered in the BEGONIA Knowledge Hub**, showing the ongoing interest generated by these activities.

Finally, although a webinar was initially planned and organised, it was postponed due to the temporary cancellation of the call for works. Nonetheless, new webinars are being prepared, focusing on dissemination and knowledge transfer. These will provide a detailed look at the three innovative use cases, emphasise best practices, and create further opportunities for exchange and engagement.

5.2. Engagement with other EU projects

As outlined in the initial strategy, collaboration with sister EU projects has been a key element of BEGONIA's stakeholder engagement activities. From the outset, several initiatives were approached through consortium networks, recommendations from the European Commission, and targeted research, laying the foundation for meaningful exchange and cooperation.

From the early stages of Use Case collection to the most recent phases, connections, knowledge exchanges, and joint activities have been actively pursued and nurtured. This effort was further reinforced during the stakeholder engagement support to WP3 and WP4, when collaboration with sister projects became more structured and frequent.

Among the various initiatives, at the time of writing this report, three stand out for the relationships established: ECLIPSE, INSIEME and EDDIE. These collaborations have progressed beyond simple information exchange to include joint visibility actions, reciprocal participation in communication activities, and preliminary discussions on potential future cooperation opportunities. At the time of writing this report, activities are still ongoing and additional plans are being developed. The aim is not only to strengthen BEGONIA's dissemination efforts but also to ensure that its results are well aligned with the broader EU research and innovation landscape.

Cooperation with INSIEME and EDDIE is still at an early stage, but discussions have already taken place to establish a more structured collaboration. By contrast, collaboration with ECLIPSE is more advanced and has already resulted in a number of concrete actions. These include the launch of a joint communication campaign using the common hashtag #ECLIPSExBEGONIA, cross-interactions on social media posts, and the publication of dedicated announcements on LinkedIn and X to highlight the start of the collaboration. Additionally, BEGONIA was featured in an interview published on the ECLIPSE blog and participated in the ECLIPSE webinar *"Four Projects, One Vision: Digital Transformation of the EU Energy System."*

Several joint activities are also in progress. These include creating a co-branded video or webinar on common topics, **organising a joint session at ENLIT 2025**, conducting an interview with ECLIPSE representatives to be published in the BEGONIA newsletter, and producing a promotional video to emphasise the importance and advantages of collaboration between projects.

Beyond engaging stakeholders, the involvement and results of sister initiatives have been highly valuable for Use Case analysis and development. **Multiple EU initiatives and frameworks have served as key references for BEGONIA, particularly the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA), the Common European Energy Data Spaces (CEEDS) initiative, and the Data Spaces Blueprint.** In practice, documents such

as the IDSA framework and CEEDS guidelines have offered crucial guidance, with their recommendations carefully incorporated into BEGONIA's work.

Although the project's analyses do not extend to implementing full-scale solutions, BEGONIA anticipates the utilisation of multiple data spaces across energy, mobility, and AI domains. To ensure scalability and interoperability, the project proposed the integration with existing external platforms and frameworks, such as **Gaia-X and IDSA**. In this context, **Gaia-X has proven particularly useful**, providing solutions to challenges related to the integration of data from diverse sources and to cross-border compliance and interoperability.

5.3. Engagement with the European Commission

Throughout the project, regular meetings were held between project representatives, HaDEA, and the European Commission to ensure ongoing alignment on progress and strategic priorities. These exchanges proved essential in refining the project's approach, validating deliverables and outcomes, and providing guidance during critical moments, such as the selection of Use Cases at the end of WP2 and WP3, and the preparation of the call for works.

Several meetings were particularly important, each serving a specific purpose and adding significant value. Their objectives and contributions are outlined below and primarily served to validate the approach without interfering in our project process.

- September 2024: Presentation of the 14 proposed Use Cases and discussion of the parameters for their selection and merging. This process facilitated the identification of the 6 final Use Cases.
- October 2024: An online meeting dedicated to presenting the shortlisted Use Cases to HaDEA and the Commission. The objective was to collect essential feedback prior to the submission of Deliverable D2.2 at the end of October.
- April 2025: This session focused on the presentation of Deliverable D3.3 and the discussion of the selection of the 3 final Use Cases. The applied selection criteria were reviewed, and further discussion took place on how these Use Cases should be included in the upcoming call for works.
- June 2025: The meeting addressed alignment efforts in support of the preparation of the call for proposals. In addition, several internal project management topics were discussed.

- July 2025: DTU took part in "The Future of Digital Investments in the EU" conference organized by the Danish Agency for Digital Government (Digst) and the European Commission. The project learnings and the synergy with other EU projects, e.g. EDDIE and INSIEME, was discussed during the "EU funding programmes synergies in practice" panel session jointly with other leading organizations.

5.4. Engagement of our external advisory board

The External Advisory Board (EAB) has played an important role in guiding BEGONIA's stakeholder engagement and ensuring alignment with broader European policy and innovation trends. The EAB consists of Dr. Zoya Pourmirza (University of Birmingham, UK), Helena Gerard (VITO, Belgium), Gonzalez Rodriguez Ignacio (Ministry of Transport and Sustainable Mobility, Spain), and Anders Pinto-Bello (smartEn, Smart Energy Europe, Belgium). Members provided feedback on the project's methodology and preliminary use case portfolio, contributing expertise across academia, national policy, and industry associations. Their input helped validate the technical, regulatory, and market relevance of the shortlisted use cases. Notably, some members participated in person during the advisory meeting held in Málaga in February 2025, which offered a valuable opportunity for direct exchange with the consortium and other stakeholders. The EAB will continue to serve as a sounding board during the remaining phases of the project, particularly in relation to piloting activities and the dissemination of results.

6. Conclusion

Stakeholder engagement has been essential to BEGONIA's progress and success in developing strong and relevant ODP use cases for cross-border, cross-sector applications in energy and transport. By mobilising expert networks, engaging national and regional authorities, collaborating with industry, and aligning with other EU initiatives, the project has ensured that its outputs reflect real needs and have broad market relevance.

The deliverable highlights several key lessons:

- Early, targeted engagement helped the consortium identify relevant high-quality use cases within a limited timeframe.
- Iterative consultation, including surveys and bilateral exchanges, allowed for the refinement and consolidation of use cases, incorporating market feedback and technical validation.
- Engagement with sister projects and advisory bodies ensured consistency with the wider EU innovation ecosystem.

D5.4 Stakeholders and industry representative engagement Summary

- Active collaboration with the European Commission and HaDEA provided strategic guidance and strengthened the project's role in preparing future calls for works.
- Maintaining stakeholder commitment requires flexibility, especially in light of external changes such as the temporary suspension of the call for works.

Moving forward, BEGONIA will continue to strengthen these relationships in preparation for WP4 piloting and the eventual transfer of knowledge to future implementing consortia. In doing so, the project will maximise its impact, ensuring that its results directly inform the European Commission's policy and funding agenda and accelerate the deployment of cross-border ODPs for energy and transport.